
FUNCTIONAL CONTINUOUS UNCERTAINTY PRINCIPLE

K. MAHESH KRISHNA

Post Doctoral Fellow

Statistics and Mathematics Unit

Indian Statistical Institute, Bangalore Centre

Karnataka 560 059, India

Email: kmaheshak@gmail.com

Date: July 24, 2023

Abstract: Let (Ω, μ) , (Δ, ν) be measure spaces. Let $(\{f_\alpha\}_{\alpha \in \Omega}, \{\tau_\alpha\}_{\alpha \in \Omega})$ and $(\{g_\beta\}_{\beta \in \Delta}, \{\omega_\beta\}_{\beta \in \Delta})$ be continuous p -Schauder frames for a Banach space \mathcal{X} . Then for every $x \in \mathcal{X} \setminus \{0\}$, we show that

(1)

$$\mu(\text{supp}(\theta_f x))^{\frac{1}{p}} \nu(\text{supp}(\theta_g x))^{\frac{1}{q}} \geq \frac{1}{\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |f_\alpha(\omega_\beta)|}, \quad \nu(\text{supp}(\theta_g x))^{\frac{1}{p}} \mu(\text{supp}(\theta_f x))^{\frac{1}{q}} \geq \frac{1}{\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |g_\beta(\tau_\alpha)|}.$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_f : \mathcal{X} \ni x &\mapsto \theta_f x \in \mathcal{L}^p(\Omega, \mu); & \theta_f x : \Omega \ni \alpha &\mapsto (\theta_f x)(\alpha) := f_\alpha(x) \in \mathbb{K}, \\ \theta_g : \mathcal{X} \ni x &\mapsto \theta_g x \in \mathcal{L}^p(\Delta, \nu); & \theta_g x : \Delta \ni \beta &\mapsto (\theta_g x)(\beta) := g_\beta(x) \in \mathbb{K} \end{aligned}$$

and q is the conjugate index of p . We call Inequality (1) as **Functional Continuous Uncertainty Principle**. It improves the Functional Donoho-Stark-Elad-Bruckstein-Ricaud-Torrésani Uncertainty Principle obtained by M. Krishna in [*arXiv:2304.03324v1, 2023*]. It also answers a question asked by Prof. Philip B. Stark to the author.

Keywords: Uncertainty Principle, Parseval Frame, Banach space.

Mathematics Subject Classification (2020): 42C15.

CONTENTS

1. Introduction	1
2. Functional Continuous Uncertainty Principle	2
3. Acknowledgments	6
References	6

1. INTRODUCTION

For $h \in \mathbb{C}^d$, let $\|h\|_0$ be the number of nonzero entries in h . Let $\hat{\cdot} : \mathbb{C}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{C}^d$ be the Fourier transform. Great and surprising inequality of Donoho and Stark which improved our life is the following.

Theorem 1.1. (*Donoho-Stark Uncertainty Principle*) [1] For every $d \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$(2) \quad \left(\frac{\|h\|_0 + \|\hat{h}\|_0}{2} \right)^2 \geq \|h\|_0 \|\hat{h}\|_0 \geq d, \quad \forall h \in \mathbb{C}^d \setminus \{0\}.$$

In 2002, Elad and Bruckstein extended Inequality (2) to pairs of orthonormal bases [2]. Given a collection $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n$ in a finite dimensional Hilbert space \mathcal{H} over \mathbb{K} (\mathbb{R} or \mathbb{C}), we define

$$\theta_\tau : \mathcal{H} \ni h \mapsto \theta_\tau h := (\langle h, \tau_j \rangle)_{j=1}^n \in \mathbb{K}^n.$$

Theorem 1.2. (Elad-Bruckstein Uncertainty Principle) [2] *Let $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n, \{\omega_j\}_{j=1}^n$ be two orthonormal bases for a finite dimensional Hilbert space \mathcal{H} . Then*

$$\left(\frac{\|\theta_\tau h\|_0 + \|\theta_\omega h\|_0}{2} \right)^2 \geq \|\theta_\tau h\|_0 \|\theta_\omega h\|_0 \geq \frac{1}{\max_{1 \leq j, k \leq n} |\langle \tau_j, \omega_k \rangle|^2}, \quad \forall h \in \mathcal{H} \setminus \{0\}.$$

In 2013, Ricaud and Torrsani showed that orthonormal bases in Theorem 1.2 can be improved to Parseval frames [6].

Theorem 1.3. (Ricaud-Torrsani Uncertainty Principle) [6] *Let $\{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n, \{\omega_j\}_{j=1}^n$ be two Parseval frames for a finite dimensional Hilbert space \mathcal{H} . Then*

$$\left(\frac{\|\theta_\tau h\|_0 + \|\theta_\omega h\|_0}{2} \right)^2 \geq \|\theta_\tau h\|_0 \|\theta_\omega h\|_0 \geq \frac{1}{\max_{1 \leq j, k \leq n} |\langle \tau_j, \omega_k \rangle|^2}, \quad \forall h \in \mathcal{H} \setminus \{0\}.$$

In 2023, author made a major improvement of Theorem 1.3.

Theorem 1.4. (Functional Donoho-Stark-Elad-Bruckstein-Ricaud-Torrsani Uncertainty Principle) [4] *Let $(\{f_j\}_{j=1}^n, \{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n)$ and $(\{g_k\}_{k=1}^m, \{\omega_k\}_{k=1}^m)$ be p -Schauder frames for a finite dimensional Banach space \mathcal{X} . Then for every $x \in \mathcal{X} \setminus \{0\}$, we have*

$$(3) \quad \|\theta_f x\|_0^{\frac{1}{p}} \|\theta_g x\|_0^{\frac{1}{q}} \geq \frac{1}{\max_{1 \leq j \leq n, 1 \leq k \leq m} |f_j(\omega_k)|} \quad \text{and} \quad \|\theta_g x\|_0^{\frac{1}{p}} \|\theta_f x\|_0^{\frac{1}{q}} \geq \frac{1}{\max_{1 \leq j \leq n, 1 \leq k \leq m} |g_k(\tau_j)|}.$$

By seeing paper [4], Prof. Philip B. Stark, Department of Statistics, University of California, Berkeley, asked the following question to the author.

Question 1.5. (Philip B. Stark) What is the infinite dimensional version of Theorem [4]?

In this paper, we derive continuous uncertainty principle for Banach spaces which contains Theorem 1.4 as a particular case and also answers Question 1.5.

2. FUNCTIONAL CONTINUOUS UNCERTAINTY PRINCIPLE

In the paper, \mathbb{K} denotes \mathbb{C} or \mathbb{R} and \mathcal{X} denotes a Banach space (need not be finite dimensional) over \mathbb{K} . Dual of \mathcal{X} is denoted by \mathcal{X}^* . Whenever $1 < p < \infty$, q denotes conjugate index of p . We recall the notion of weak integral also known as Pettis integrals [7]. Let (Ω, μ) be a measure space and \mathcal{X} be a Banach space. A function $f : \Omega \rightarrow \mathcal{X}$ is said to be weak integrable or Pettis integrable if following conditions hold.

- (i) For every $\phi \in \mathcal{X}^*$, the map $\phi f : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{K}$ is measurable and $\phi f \in \mathcal{L}^1(\Omega, \mu)$.
- (ii) For every measurable subset $E \in \Omega$, there exists an (unique) element $x_E \in \mathcal{X}$ such that

$$\phi(x_E) = \int_E \phi(f(\alpha)) d\mu(\alpha), \quad \forall \phi \in \mathcal{X}^*.$$

The element $x_E \in \mathcal{X}$ is denoted by $\int_E f(\alpha) d\mu(\alpha)$. With this notion, we have

$$\phi \left(\int_E f(\alpha) d\mu(\alpha) \right) = \int_E \phi(f(\alpha)) d\mu(\alpha), \quad \forall \phi \in \mathcal{X}^*, \forall E \in \Omega.$$

We need the following continuous version of p-Schauder frames [4].

Definition 2.1. Let (Ω, μ) be a measure space. Let $\{\tau_\alpha\}_{\alpha \in \Omega}$ be a collection in a Banach space \mathcal{X} and $\{f_\alpha\}_{\alpha \in \Omega}$ be a collection in \mathcal{X}^* . The pair $(\{f_\alpha\}_{\alpha \in \Omega}, \{\tau_\alpha\}_{\alpha \in \Omega})$ is said to be a **continuous p-Schauder frame** for \mathcal{X} ($1 < p < \infty$) if the following holds.

- (i) For every $x \in \mathcal{X}$, the map $\Omega \ni \alpha \mapsto f_\alpha(x) \in \mathbb{K}$ is measurable.
- (ii) For every $x \in \mathcal{X}$,

$$\|x\|^p = \int_{\Omega} |f_\alpha(x)|^p d\mu(\alpha).$$

- (iii) For every $x \in \mathcal{X}$, the map $\Omega \ni \alpha \mapsto f_\alpha(x)\tau_\alpha \in \mathbb{K}$ is weakly measurable.
- (iv) For every $x \in \mathcal{X}$,

$$x = \int_{\Omega} f_\alpha(x)\tau_\alpha d\mu(\alpha),$$

where the integral is weak integral.

We note that condition (i) in Definition 2.1 says that the map

$$\theta_f : \mathcal{X} \ni x \mapsto \theta_f x \in \mathcal{L}^p(\Omega, \mu); \quad \theta_f x : \Omega \ni \alpha \mapsto (\theta_f x)(\alpha) := f_\alpha(x) \in \mathbb{K}$$

is a linear isometry. Following is the fundamental result of this paper.

Theorem 2.2. (Functional Continuous Uncertainty Principle) Let (Ω, μ) , (Δ, ν) be measure spaces. Let $(\{f_\alpha\}_{\alpha \in \Omega}, \{\tau_\alpha\}_{\alpha \in \Omega})$ and $(\{g_\beta\}_{\beta \in \Delta}, \{\omega_\beta\}_{\beta \in \Delta})$ be continuous p-Schauder frames for a Banach space \mathcal{X} . Then for every $x \in \mathcal{X} \setminus \{0\}$, we have

$$(4) \quad \mu(\text{supp}(\theta_f x))^{\frac{1}{p}} \nu(\text{supp}(\theta_g x))^{\frac{1}{q}} \geq \frac{1}{\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |f_\alpha(\omega_\beta)|}, \quad \nu(\text{supp}(\theta_g x))^{\frac{1}{p}} \mu(\text{supp}(\theta_f x))^{\frac{1}{q}} \geq \frac{1}{\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |g_\beta(\tau_\alpha)|}.$$

Proof. Let $x \in \mathcal{X} \setminus \{0\}$ and q be the conjugate index of p . First using θ_f is an isometry and later using θ_g is an isometry, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
\|x\|^p &= \|\theta_f x\|^p = \int_{\Omega} |f_{\alpha}(x)|^p d\mu(\alpha) = \int_{\text{supp}(\theta_f x)} |f_{\alpha}(x)|^p d\mu(\alpha) \\
&= \int_{\text{supp}(\theta_f x)} \left| f_{\alpha} \left(\int_{\Delta} g_{\beta}(x) \omega_{\beta} d\nu(\beta) \right) \right|^p d\mu(\alpha) = \int_{\text{supp}(\theta_f x)} \left| \int_{\Delta} g_{\beta}(x) f_{\alpha}(\omega_{\beta}) d\nu(\beta) \right|^p d\mu(\alpha) \\
&= \int_{\text{supp}(\theta_f x)} \left| \int_{\text{supp}(\theta_g x)} g_{\beta}(x) f_{\alpha}(\omega_{\beta}) d\nu(\beta) \right|^p d\mu(\alpha) \leq \int_{\text{supp}(\theta_f x)} \left(\int_{\text{supp}(\theta_g x)} |g_{\beta}(x) f_{\alpha}(\omega_{\beta})| d\nu(\beta) \right)^p d\mu(\alpha) \\
&\leq \left(\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |f_{\alpha}(\omega_{\beta})| \right)^p \int_{\text{supp}(\theta_f x)} \left(\int_{\text{supp}(\theta_g x)} |g_{\beta}(x)| d\nu(\beta) \right)^p d\mu(\alpha) \\
&= \left(\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |f_{\alpha}(\omega_{\beta})| \right)^p \mu(\text{supp}(\theta_f x)) \left(\int_{\text{supp}(\theta_g x)} |g_{\beta}(x)| d\nu(\beta) \right)^p \\
&\leq \left(\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |f_{\alpha}(\omega_{\beta})| \right)^p \mu(\text{supp}(\theta_f x)) \left(\int_{\text{supp}(\theta_g x)} |g_{\beta}(x)|^p d\nu(\beta) \right)^{\frac{p}{p}} \left(\int_{\text{supp}(\theta_g x)} 1^q d\nu(\beta) \right)^{\frac{p}{q}} \\
&= \left(\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |f_{\alpha}(\omega_{\beta})| \right)^p \mu(\text{supp}(\theta_f x)) \|\theta_g x\|^p \nu(\text{supp}(\theta_g x))^{\frac{p}{q}} \\
&= \left(\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |f_{\alpha}(\omega_{\beta})| \right)^p \mu(\text{supp}(\theta_f x)) \|x\|^p \nu(\text{supp}(\theta_g x))^{\frac{p}{q}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore

$$\frac{1}{\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |f_{\alpha}(\omega_{\beta})|} \leq \mu(\text{supp}(\theta_f x))^{\frac{1}{p}} \nu(\text{supp}(\theta_g x))^{\frac{1}{q}}.$$

On the other way, first using θ_g is an isometry and θ_f is an isometry, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 \|x\|^p &= \|\theta_g x\|^p = \int_{\Delta} |g_{\beta}(x)|^p d\nu(\beta) = \int_{\text{supp}(\theta_g x)} |g_{\beta}(x)|^p d\nu(\beta) \\
 &= \int_{\text{supp}(\theta_g x)} \left| g_{\beta} \left(\int_{\Omega} f_{\alpha}(x) \tau_{\alpha} d\mu(\alpha) \right) \right|^p d\nu(\beta) = \int_{\text{supp}(\theta_g x)} \left| \int_{\Omega} f_{\alpha}(x) g_{\beta}(\tau_{\alpha}) d\mu(\alpha) \right|^p d\nu(\beta) \\
 &= \int_{\text{supp}(\theta_g x)} \left| \int_{\text{supp}(\theta_f x)} f_{\alpha}(x) g_{\beta}(\tau_{\alpha}) d\mu(\alpha) \right|^p d\nu(\beta) \leq \int_{\text{supp}(\theta_g x)} \left(\int_{\text{supp}(\theta_f x)} |f_{\alpha}(x) g_{\beta}(\tau_{\alpha})| d\mu(\alpha) \right)^p d\nu(\beta) \\
 &\leq \left(\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |g_{\beta}(\tau_{\alpha})| \right)^p \int_{\text{supp}(\theta_g x)} \left(\int_{\text{supp}(\theta_f x)} |f_{\alpha}(x)| d\mu(\alpha) \right)^p d\nu(\beta) \\
 &= \left(\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |g_{\beta}(\tau_{\alpha})| \right)^p \nu(\text{supp}(\theta_g x)) \left(\int_{\text{supp}(\theta_f x)} |f_{\alpha}(x)| d\mu(\alpha) \right)^p \\
 &\leq \left(\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |g_{\beta}(\tau_{\alpha})| \right)^p \nu(\text{supp}(\theta_g x)) \left(\int_{\text{supp}(\theta_f x)} |f_{\alpha}(x)|^p d\mu(\alpha) \right)^{\frac{p}{q}} \left(\int_{\text{supp}(\theta_f x)} 1^q d\mu(\alpha) \right)^{\frac{p}{q}} \\
 &= \left(\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |g_{\beta}(\tau_{\alpha})| \right)^p \nu(\text{supp}(\theta_g x)) \|\theta_f x\|^p \mu(\text{supp}(\theta_f x))^{\frac{p}{q}} \\
 &= \left(\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |g_{\beta}(\tau_{\alpha})| \right)^p \nu(\text{supp}(\theta_g x)) \|x\|^p \mu(\text{supp}(\theta_f x))^{\frac{p}{q}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore

$$\frac{1}{\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |g_{\beta}(\tau_{\alpha})|} \leq \nu(\text{supp}(\theta_g x))^{\frac{1}{p}} \mu(\text{supp}(\theta_f x))^{\frac{1}{q}}.$$

□

Corollary 2.3. *Let (Ω, μ) , (Δ, ν) be measure spaces. Let $\{\tau_{\alpha}\}_{\alpha \in \Omega}$ and $\{\omega_{\beta}\}_{\beta \in \Delta}$ be Parseval continuous frames for a Hilbert space \mathcal{H} . Then for every $h \in \mathcal{H} \setminus \{0\}$, we have*

$$\mu(\text{supp}(\theta_{\tau} h)) \nu(\text{supp}(\theta_{\omega} h)) \geq \frac{1}{\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |\langle \omega_{\beta}, \tau_{\alpha} \rangle|^2}, \quad \nu(\text{supp}(\theta_{\omega} h)) \mu(\text{supp}(\theta_{\tau} h)) \geq \frac{1}{\sup_{\alpha \in \Omega, \beta \in \Delta} |\langle \tau_{\alpha}, \omega_{\beta} \rangle|^2},$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
 \theta_{\tau} : \mathcal{H} \ni h &\mapsto \theta_{\tau} h \in \mathcal{L}^2(\Omega, \mu); & \theta_{\tau} h : \Omega \ni \alpha &\mapsto (\theta_{\tau} h)(\alpha) := \langle h, \tau_{\alpha} \rangle \in \mathbb{K}, \\
 \theta_{\omega} : \mathcal{H} \ni h &\mapsto \theta_{\omega} h \in \mathcal{L}^2(\Delta, \nu); & \theta_{\omega} h : \Delta \ni \beta &\mapsto (\theta_{\omega} h)(\beta) := \langle h, \omega_{\beta} \rangle \in \mathbb{K}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 2.4. *Theorem 1.4 follows from Theorem 2.2.*

Proof. Let $(\{f_j\}_{j=1}^n, \{\tau_j\}_{j=1}^n)$ and $(\{g_k\}_{k=1}^m, \{\omega_k\}_{k=1}^m)$ be p-Schauder frames for a finite dimensional Banach space \mathcal{X} . Define $\Omega := \{1, \dots, n\}$ and $\Delta := \{1, \dots, m\}$. Take μ as counting measure on Ω and ν as counting measure on Δ . □

Theorem 2.2 brings the following question.

Question 2.5. (i) Let (Ω, μ) , (Δ, ν) be measure spaces, \mathcal{X} be a Banach space and $p > 1$. For which pairs of continuous p -Schauder frames $(\{f_\alpha\}_{\alpha \in \Omega}, \{\tau_\alpha\}_{\alpha \in \Omega})$ and $(\{g_\beta\}_{\beta \in \Delta}, \{\omega_\beta\}_{\beta \in \Delta})$ for \mathcal{X} , we have equality in Inequality (4)?

(ii) What is the version of Theorem 2.2 for $0 < p \leq 1$ and $p = \infty$?

If we can derive the uncertainty principles derived in [3] and [5] for p -Schauder frames, then we hope that we can get continuous versions of them.

3. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Author thanks Prof. Philip B. Stark, Department of Statistics, University of California, Berkeley for asking Question 1.5. Author believes that this paper exists because of Question 1.5.

REFERENCES

- [1] David L. Donoho and Philip B. Stark. Uncertainty principles and signal recovery. *SIAM J. Appl. Math.*, 49(3):906–931, 1989.
- [2] Michael Elad and Alfred M. Bruckstein. A generalized uncertainty principle and sparse representation in pairs of bases. *IEEE Trans. Inform. Theory*, 48(9):2558–2567, 2002.
- [3] K. Mahesh Krishna. Functional Donoho-Stark approximate-support uncertainty principle. *arXiv:2307.01215v1 [math.FA]* 1 July, 2023.
- [4] K. Mahesh Krishna. Functional Donoho-Stark-Elad-Bruckstein-Ricaud-Torrésani uncertainty principle. *arXiv:2304.03324v1 [math.FA]* 5 April, 2023.
- [5] K. Mahesh Krishna. Functional Ghobber-Jaming uncertainty principle. *arXiv:2306.01014v1 [math.FA]* 1 June, 2023.
- [6] Benjamin Ricaud and Bruno Torrèsani. Refined support and entropic uncertainty inequalities. *IEEE Trans. Inform. Theory*, 59(7):4272–4279, 2013.
- [7] Michel Talagrand. Pettis integral and measure theory. *Mem. Amer. Math. Soc.*, 51(307):ix+224, 1984.